

The Use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) in the Teaching of Tragedy "Antigone" by Sophocles

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Abstract: In this study we aim to present a teaching scenario in the lesson of ancient Greek "Antigone" of Sophocles, in which ICT is used as a tool for the cultivation of cognitive, communicative and metacognitive skills. The proposed scenario will be implemented with the exploitation of the collaborative teaching method, in which the emphasis is placed not only on the result but also on the process itself. The product which is produced, of course, is always richer and more creative than what each student could have achieved on his own. The role of the teacher is to concentrate on a problem solving process in a context of authentic learning, where children have the opportunity to express their opinions, listen to others' ideas and collaborate with each other in order to solve a problem of real life.

Keywords: Authentic Learning, Metacognitive Skills, Social Constructivism, Ancient Greek

Introduction

The theoretical approach upon which the teaching proposal is based is social constructivism. According to the theory of social constructivism, particular importance is given to the role of social and cultural factors in the creation of knowledge, the process of learning and the development of the individual (Vygotsky, 1978). According to Vygotsky (1978) "each individual's thought is built on the basis of social behavioral". Social constructivism interprets learning as a social and cooperative process (Gergan, 1999). Students gain knowledge when working collaboratively and knowledge-minding take into account the inflows of social behavioral rules, tradition and interaction with other important factors.

In the proposed teaching scenario we have adopted the socio-structural framework for cooperative learning processes, ie the understanding of the nature of learning in a cooperative environment both at an individual and a social level (Hunter, 2006). The basic principles of learning according to the theory of constructivism are:

- Learning is achieved within a social environment (Vygotsky, 1978)
- Each person forms his own representations for knowledge (Dewey, 1933).
- Active learning techniques are used in the learning process
- The starting point for learning is the pupils' needs and particular interests

- The learning process exploits the pre-existing experiences of students (Agelopoulos, Karagiannis, Karantzis, Frangoulis, Fokas, 2002).

In the context of the constructivist teaching approach, particular emphasis is placed on: a) the understanding of the concepts and their holistic approach, b) the exploitation of the interests of the students, c) the processing of primary sources, d) pupil utilization, e) teacher – student interaction, f) the collaborative learning process (Savery & Duffy, 1995; Brooks & Brooks, 1999; Jonasen & Rohrer-Murphy, 1999). Thus, emphasis is placed on the social symbolic nature of knowledge that the individual builds in realistic conditions both in collaboration with his classmates and the teacher. The difference in the ideas and opinions of the members of the group causes instability, resulting in the reorganization of the previous knowledge and the conquest of the new in a climate of communication and cooperation.

The learner learns mainly in the living environment. The richer it is in stimuli and educational opportunities, the more interactions it has, the more likely it will be for the student to develop his / her linguistic and communicative skills. The teacher can no longer be the only source of knowledge. The rates at which information spreads and the increased accessibility to it negate the traditional role of the teacher as a transmitter of knowledge. He has a duty not to offer knowledge, but to equip the student with the necessary skills to seek knowledge autonomously,

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control it, challenge it, accept it and adapt it to the demands of its environment (Agelopoulos, Fragoulis, et al., 2002)

In addition to the role of the teacher, the form of the lesson needs to change. The lesson must be attractive, rich in stimuli and convincing regarding its usefulness. Because of the many interests and activities that children have to choose autonomously, they will devote their time. Here is the modern school's bet, whether it can be a pole of attraction for them (Agelopoulos, Fragoulis, et al., 2002). Authentic learning can be created in such an environment. In the field of education, authentic learning refers to a variety of educational techniques that focus on linking the knowledge that pupils acquire in school with issues, problems and applications of the real world. The basic concept of authentic learning is based on the perception that pupils may be more interested in what they learn, more willing to acquire new knowledge and skills and therefore better prepared for their later school life and professional career if this knowledge and skills reflect real life are practical and useful and address issues that are important and applicable to the real life (<http://edglossary.org/authentic-learning>).

Students who are engaged in authentic activities will be able to cultivate cognitive, communicative and metacognitive skills. The term "metacognition" has three main aspects: metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive skills and metacognitive experiences (Kostaridou -Euclides, 2005).

- Metacognitive knowledge is about updating and understanding the pupil's image of himself.
- Metacognitive skills relate to self-directed control of the understanding of project requirements
- Metacognitive experiences refer to cognitive or thymic experiences experienced by the individual during his or her work with the cognitive work (Euclid, 2005; Flavell, 1979).

In cognitive and metacognitive skills are included: problem solving, critical thinking, questioning, finding information, critical observation, effective use of information, research, construction, inventing, analyzing and presenting data, communication, spoken and written expression, reflection and self-assessment (Kasimatis, Ferentis, 2005). Particular emphasis should be placed on the development of critical thinking, ie the cultivation of pupils' ability to evaluate ideas and opinions with a view to selecting the best. Emphasis should also be placed on the development of creative thinking, ie the cultivation of ideas for producing ideas.

In the literature lessons, in particular the hunter's language lesson (2006), "the use of digital

technologies can contribute to the diverse development of written expression skills in learning environments that highlight the communicative dimension of language learning, features provided for creating links between texts and sources through hyperlinks". Students can exploit resources by interpreting historical events, explaining specific questions, and working out findings and specific situations.

A prerequisite for learning is to create an appropriate climate that favors collaboration and communication among subjects involved in the learning process. The main tool for this is computer aid. The form of teaching is changing. Weight is shifted from the suggestion that uses the table to the interaction between student and classmate, student and teacher (Hunter, 2006).

The knowledge will become social, as the class community will discover it and then validate it after argument and acceptance. To achieve this, we recommend the whole classroom be organized into individual groups. In this way:

- The internal dialogue is promoted to each group.
- Cooperation is favored.
- Communication is promoted through the exchange of views on how each member of the group understands the activity in question.
- Each group issues its own questions, which are then asked to be answered by the whole classroom.

1. Proposed technological tools

The use of technology in education has undoubted value when accompanied by an appropriate pedagogical scenario and it is implemented by teachers with pedagogical training in the teaching of ICT. Technology can change the way students get access to important ideas and material without the long-term access to them, as was the traditional way of teaching.

According to Bosniadou (2005): "Using a computer in the presentation of a module can teach abstract concepts to tangible - manageable, reveal their possibilities and constraints, and relate them to the daily situations they represent and link them to others representations of the same information". Of course, the computer itself does not provide the desired results. We therefore need an appropriate strategy that will serve our goals.

The computer is not literate itself but can serve the promotion of very different educational and philosophical views (Papert, 1991). It can be used to create opportunities to practice quality thinking in a learning environment different from traditional teaching.

3. Designing of the Teaching Proposal

We recommend that the lesson be held one hour per week in the class of the ancient Greek of the 2nd Grade Lyceum. Part of this scenario can be done in the computer lab with students in triplets per computer. Computer use is essential as it fosters collaboration between students and dynamically engages the learner in activities such as information search, classification, interpretation, feedback, analysis and synthesis.

Students on the computer will process a worksheet and a rating sheet. Student assessment will use objective types of questions designed in the free hot potatoes software, which will provide feedback to students. Each group will work independently by following the worksheet instructions. It searches for information, discusses, processes data that it finds and answers in writing to specific questions. The feedback that will be offered by the software itself may be the following "What wrong am I doing here?" "Does the solution make sense?" "What are the similarities / differences between this problem and the others that we have solved?" The actions we choose concentrate on the dialogue and the collective behavior of pupils, as they are jointly invited to cooperate in order to respond to them (Fragoulis & Frantzis, 2010).

Grouping is necessary because the objective of the activities - actions we choose is to achieve and favor collaboration. The whole team will work together to complete the project and everyone will be involved, making proposals and taking roles within it. The activity we choose, we believe will attract the interest of children as it is connected with language and communication, an integral part of our lives.

Purpose: The term "which parts of the tragedy" is one of the most important tragedies, according to Aristotle. In our work we will describe the definition of this concept and look at its individual terms.

Expected Results

After attending the course students should be able to:

- describe the concepts of "ethos", "morals", "opsis", "word" in tragedy
- interpret the morality of Sophocles' "Antigone" tragedy as well as any other tragedy.
- identify and interpret Sophocles' tragedy "Antigone" as well as any other tragedy.
- identify and interpret the "word" in Sophocles's "Antigone" tragedy, as well as in any other tragedy.
- draw conclusions through the exploration and exploitation of sources.
- to realize the diachronic dimension of the Greek language

1st Activity

Many words that today in Modern Greek mean things, actions, ideas, etc., or attribute a characteristic do not in all cases have the same meaning as they used to. We reach this conclusion if we pay attention to their etymology or refer to a dictionary of our ancient or medieval language. The findings are similar if we consult a modern dictionary that also refers to the earlier meaning of words eg. In the "anger" entry in the dictionary of the ancient Greek language by Lidell and Scott (1997) it is cited as the soul, the spirit, the elements of life, sensation or thought. On the contrary, according to Babiniotis (1998) "anger is the intense dissatisfaction, which manifests in an equally intense way, the crisis-anger explosion".

The character and the attitude of the heroes, as manifested by their reasons, actions and choices when they are in a dilemma or in danger. Aristotle believes that morals should be good, to express a benevolent option, appropriate, to agree with the age, sex and social order of the heroes and similar and smooth, ie the heroes do not show sudden and unreasonable transitions. According to the dimension that Aristotle attributes to the notion of "ethos", call/characterize Creon in verses 162-210.

2nd Activity

The following excerpts of ancient Greek texts (given in translation by clicking on the title of each) record the cultural course of man. Read them in relation to Antigone's First Stand and report your findings on an essay, you can upload to your e-class or your school website (Supposedly an e-class is available).

- a) Aeschylus, *Supply Bound*, f. 436-506
- b) *Entrance, Works and Days*, f. 109-201
- c) Evripidis, *Iketides*, p. 195-215
- d) Plato, *Protagoras*, 321c-322c

3rd Activity

In our everyday life we use the word "face" eg. "The face of this man is terrifying. The face of the patient was pale. "It comes from the verb "see" and we can find it in complex words such as facade, optic etc. "Taking in mind the current meaning of this word, the etymology and the difference in the meaning of the words between ancient and modern Greek can you interpret the meaning of this word in ancient Greek?"

4th Activity

We use as an example for understanding the face (the way someone looks like) two photographs representing elements of the face, such as the masks and the clothing of the heroes of a tragedy.

Locate the elements of "face" in verses 1-22 of the "Antigone" tragedy

5th Activity

Compare the Sophocles' prologue with the prologue of another ancient tragedy, Euripides' "Electra" concerning them and try to find similarities and differences. Record the answers in the notebook.

To study these texts, use the Google search engine and write <https://www.mikrosapoplous.gr/>. Choose Ancient Texts, including Sophocles' "Electra" and Euripides' "Electra", from which you will read the first 150 verses.

6th Activity

Collect photographic material from the internet. Start your research with an internet search engine by writing the words "tragedy", "dance", "chorus". You can sort the photos by gender, style, step, type of show, and then write appropriate captions under each photo.

7th Activity

You are given the essence of the modern Greek "word". Which verb does it come from? Based on its etymology, can you give a definition to it and assume the importance it would have in ancient Greek? Then locate the main speech format in the following verses as well as in verses 100-162:

"Behold, whether it be the same, or that nowadays this friends come to us"

8th Activity

Search on the Greek Language Portal <http://www.greek-language.gr/greekLang/index.html> two excerpts from any tragedies you wish of two different tragic poets and characterize their style by identifying similarities and differences.

Discussion - Conclusions

Students build on pre-existing knowledge in the context of constructivism. They develop cognitively, emotionally and aesthetically, ie holistically. This development contributes to a deeper understanding not only of themselves but also of the reality that surrounds them (Mega, 2011: 62).

Trainees within the method learn to recognize and respect the ideas, perceptions and values of others as they perceive and analyze in depth. At the same time they acquire empathy by understanding the thoughts, feelings and system of values of the "others", by comparing their value system to their own. Using the method, they more fully understand the complexity of the events and interpret them more fully (Fragoulis, 2014). This process contributes to the transformation of their initial assumptions in relation to the subject under consideration.

The use of the method and its ongoing assessment is related to reflection, is defined as a meta-activity stemming from the review of past actions and carried out either by the individual (implementing the actions) himself/ herself or by other community members. This review often gives rise to a change in viewpoint and causes the creation of a new mental construct (Hershkowitz & Schwarz, 1999). Through the metacognitive strategies that students develop, they can be lead to the right execution of a project and the "building" of knowledge by monitoring its progress, evaluating and applying knowledge to new situations.

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